

ISSN 2278-4004

UGC CARE List Journal

प्राच्या PRĀCYĀ

A Peer Reviewed (Refereed) Journal on Sanskrit & Related Studies

Volume - XVI

VĀSTUVIDYĀVIŚEṢAṂKAḤ
वास्तुविद्याविशेषांकः

धन्योऽयं भारतो देशः धन्येयं सुरभारती ।
उपासकाः वयं यत्र धन्या अहो परम्परा ॥

DEPARTMENT OF SANSKRIT
MDK Girls' College, Dibrugarh, Assam
2024

ISSN 2278-4004

UGC CARE List Journal

प्राच्या PRĀCYĀ

A Peer Reviewed (Refereed) Journal on Sanskrit & Related Studies

Volume - XVI

VĀSTUVIDYĀVIŚEṢAṂKAḤ
वास्तुविद्याविशेषांकः

धन्योऽयं भारतो देशः धन्येयं सुरभारती ।
उपासकाः तयं यत्र धन्या अहो परम्परा ॥

DEPARTMENT OF SANSKRIT
MDK Girls' College, Dibrugarh, Assam
2024

PRĀCYĀ (ISSN 2278-4004), the annual Peer Reviewed **UGC CARE List Journal on Sanskrit & Related Studies**, brought out by the **Department of Sanskrit, MDK Girls' College, Dibrugarh (Assam)**, published by **MDKG College**.

ADVISORY BOARD

- ❑ **Prof. Malinee Goswami**, Former Vice Chancellor, Assam Women's University, Jorhat, Assam (India)
- ❑ **Prof. Dipak Kumar Sharma**, Former Vice Chancellor, Kumar Bhaskarvarma Sanskrit & Ancient Studies University, Nalbari, Assam, India
- ❑ **Dr Anupjyoti Bharali**, Principal, MDKG College, Dibrugarh, Assam
- ❑ **Dr V. Kameswari**, Former Director, Kuppuswamy Shastri Research Institute, Chennai, India
- ❑ **Prof. Mukta Biswas**, Dept of Sanskrit (Retired), Gauhati University, Guwahati, Assam (India)
- ❑ **Prof. Sujata Purkayastha**, Dept of Sanskrit (Retired), Gauhati University, Guwahati, Assam (India)
- ❑ **Prof. Manjula Devi**, Dept of Sanskrit, Gauhati University, Guwahati, Assam (India)
- ❑ **Prof. Shyamananda Mishra**, Dept of Sahitya, Faculty of Sanskrit Vidya-Dharm Vigyan, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, UP, India

EDITORIAL BOARD

Chief Editor :

Dr. Manashi Sharma, Vice Principal, MDKG College, Dibrugarh

Members :

Dr. Binima Buzarbaruah, Associate Professor, Dept of Sanskrit, Gauhati University

Dr. Shekhar Purkayastha, Assistant Professor, Dept of Bengali, MDKG College

Dr. Rupali Majumder, Assistant Professor, Dept of Philosophy, MDKG College

Dr. Rizia B. Laskar, Assistant Professor, Dept of English, MDKG College

Dr. Uma Devi, Associate Professor, Dept of Hindi, Gauhati University

Year of Publication : September, 2024

© Principal, MDKG College, Dibrugarh & The Chief Editor, **Prācyā**.

Mailing Address :

Dr Manashi Sharma,

Dept of Sanskrit, MDKG College,

K. C. Gogoi Path, Dibrugarh-786001, Assam, India;

Mobile: 7086009302. (Email: pracya.dib@gmail.com)

Printed by : S. D. Printers, Kalibari Road, Dibrugarh. (☎ 94015127172)

CONTENTS

<u>Title of Articles</u>	<u>Page No.</u>
1. Glimpses of the Mānasāra and the Mayamata– Some Facets – Dr. Binima Buzarbaruah	9-16
2. Theatre Architecture of Ancient India and the Graeco-Roman World – Dr. Pranjal Sharma Bashishtha – Dr. Goutam Sarmah	17-27
3. Educational Significance of Stūpa in Buddhism – Dr. Abilupta Padmanathan Gohain	28-34
4. LĀKSĀGRHA: An Enigmatic Architecture in the Mahābhārata – Ramya Bhatt	35-41
5. The Perception of the Viṣṇudharmottarapurāṇa Regarding Temple – Dr. Bhagyashree Sarma	42-51
6. The Literary and Architectural Depiction of Hair Styles – Dr. V. Yamuna Devi	52-60
7. Earthquake Resistant Building Codes in Ancient Indian – Nirupama Tripathi	61-72
8. The Architecture of the Śrīyantra and the Intrinsic Philosophy behind it – Dr. Rashmi Rekha Goswami	73-81
9. ṢADVARGAS of a Temple Structure – K. Vidyuta	82-89
10. Vāstuśāstra, the source of Modern Construction with special – Dr. Mridusmita Devi	90-97
11. PADMA: Floral Motif in Ancient Indian Architecture – Dr. V. Preethi	98-106
12. Units of Measurement as Reflected in the Hindu Texts and – Gouranga Chowdhury	107-113
13. AṢṬA-VĪRA-STHĀNAS of Lord Śiva: A Sculptural Perspective – V. R. Srinivasan	114-122

CONTENTS

<u>Title of Articles</u>	<u>Page No.</u>
1. The Terminological issues of Temple Vāstu Śilpa: A Linguistic Approach ... – Dipankar Bhattacharya	123-130
2. GRHAPRAVEŚA and VĀSTUŚĀNTI–Its Need and Benefits – Laxman Majhi	131-140
3. Iconography- A prominent wing of Temple Architecture; from the point – Ashlesha Goswami	141-151
4. VĀSTUVIDYĀ and NĀṬYAŚĀSTRA: An interconnection – Nikita Das – Olympica Rajbongshi	152-158
5. VĀSTU in the ŚUKRANĪTI – A Study – Abhijit Sarma	159-167
6. Animals in the Temple Architecture in Early Medieval Assam – Sanjoy Das	168-177
7. Influence of Vāstuvidyā on Kerala's Temple Architecture – Sruthi. S	178-186
8. Embedding Human Beings with the Environment: An Introspection – Bitupon Borah	187-195
9. ভাৰতীয় বাস্তুশাস্ত্ৰ আৰু চাংকং ফুকনৰ বুৰঞ্জীৰ তুলনামূলক অধ্যয়ন – ড° ববী দাউদুং লাংথাছা – ইব্ৰাহিম আনশাৰি	196-205
10. Contribution of Ahom rulers to the development of Secular Architecture – Krishna Moni Borah	206-211
11. वास्तुरत्नावल्यां गृहद्वारनिर्णयाध्यायविश्लेषणम् – Barasha Patgiri	212-218
12. LIST OF CONTRIBUTORS	219-220
13. Book Review - Town Planning In Ancient India (English) – Author: Dr. Vasumati Rajaram	221-222

GRHAPRAVEŚĀ and VĀSTUŚĀNTI – Its Need and Benefits

– Laxman Majhi

This research paper explores the significance of grhapraveśa, procedure and the implementation of measures to mitigate vāstudośas in residential architecture. Vāstu, a traditional Indian architectural system, emphasizes harmonizing spatial arrangements with natural elements to enhance the well-being and prosperity of occupants. The paper examines various vāstu principles related to grhapraveśa procedure and identifies common defects that may disrupt energy flow and create imbalances in the living environment. The study investigates effective strategies and remedies to rectify vāstudośas in grhapraveśa configurations.

Keywords: Grhapraveśa, vāstu, architectural design, spatial arrangement, energy flow, harmonization, defects, mitigation strategies, residential architecture.

Introduction:

The body of human beings or rather all the beings living in this entire world and including the substances produced in the universe are directly and indirectly made up of the five elements (earth, water, fire, air and sky). According to vāstu science, any house, building etc. is also made up of five elements. Sages and saints have described the best method of house construction by properly combining the five elements in the form of architecture.

The human body constituting physical and mental components is subject to disorders and to solve them, we do appropriate medical, spiritual and other treatments and completely restore health. Similarly, in the case of a house we reside, there may arise various disorders naturally and artificially in the form of vāstudośas. At times it can be observed that the residents of some houses are constantly suffering from problems like family issues, financial loss, members of the house continuously suffering from diseases, work being delayed, lack of interest in the house, increase in negative energy, etc. If these are observed in one's house, then vāstudośa can also be the reason behind all these discrepancies. The methods described in the scriptures for resolving these vāstu related defects are vāstuśānti, grhapraveśa etc.

Purpose of performing *VāstuŚānti* and *GṛhaPraveśaPūjā*:

Any construction of structure like a house or a building or temple involves the five elements of nature and a disturbance in them. Hence after the completion of the construction work of a house, *gṛhapraveśa* and *vāstuśānti* are to be performed for auspiciousness and to mitigate the disturbance caused in the five elements. The *VāstuRatnākara* mentions that by performing *vāstuśāntipūjā*, the house is renewed with favorable positive energy and the house-owner becomes prosperous and happy and will never again face any sorrow:

yaḥpūjayedvāstumananyabhaktyānatasyaduḥkhaṃbhavatīhakiñcit /

jīvatyasauvarṣaśataṃsukhenasvargenarastiṣṭhatikalpamekam ॥¹

Similarly, the ancient *Ācārya* has also described that the person who enters the house without performing *vāstupūjā* and does not respect the architects and *sūtradhāras* who have constructed the house, then such a person will suffer from varied types of leprosy for seven births and live in hell even after death:

vāstupūjāvihīnaścasutradhārairvinātathā /

saptajanmabhavetkuṣṭhisatataṃmarakamavrajat ॥²

Thus from the above mention it is clear that the sages wanted the owners to thank the architects and the *sūtradhāras* and honour them for their hard work.

In *vāstuśāntipūjā* of a house, in fact, is only the worship of all the five elements (earth, water, fire, air and sky) directly or indirectly. *Vāstuśāntipūjā* is performed for the prevention of *vāstu* related defects related to land, building etc. in the house and for happiness, prosperity and all round welfare.

Under *vāstuśāntipūjā*, *pīthas* (*maṇḍals*) of all the main Gods and Goddesses are made in different rooms of the building and they are invoked, worshiped, offered, sacrificial fire, etc. as per the scriptures. The lords of directions - *Navagraha*, *catuḥṣaṣṭī* (sixty-four) *yoginī* worship, *kṣetrapāla* worship, deities invoked from the seven worlds as well as natural powers are duly worshipped.

According to *Vāstuśāstra*, any kind of defect in the architecture can be rectified. *Vāstuśānti* is performed to remove defects of any environmental issue or architectural defect. Before the house warming *pūjā*, people perform *vāstupūjā* to appease the Gods and demigods who are said to reside in a plot where the construction was carried out.

Time to perform *VāstuŚānti*:

According to *ĀcāryaSūtradhāra* Mandan, the author of many *Vāstuśāstra* texts, *vāstuśānti* should be done during five occasions at different stages of construction. Initially, *vāstuhoma* should be done at the time of inauguration of a building or a

temple. Again, at the time of land clearing too the *vāstuhoma* is to be conducted. Once again, at the time of installation of doors and for the fourth time at the time of installation of pillars, the *vāstuhoma* has to be done. Finally, at the time of entering the house, *Vāstuyajña* should be performed:

*bhavanapurāsurāṅgāmsūtraṅepūrvamuktaḥkathita
ihaprthivyāḥśodhane ca dvitīyaḥ |
tadanumukhaniveśestambhasaṅropaṅesyāt
bhavanavasanaḥkālepañcadhāvāstuyajñāḥ ||*³

It is also described in the *MatsyaPurāna* that it is beneficial to perform rituals like *vāstuśānti* and *grhasāntihoma* after reconstruction of a dilapidated (old) building; at the time of planting a garden; at the time of entering a new house; at the time of moving from one place to another and at the time of installation of a door in the house:

*jīrṇoddhāretathodyānetathāgrhaniveśane ||
navaprāsādabhavaneprāsādaparivartane |
dvārābhivartanetatvatprāsādeṣugrheṣu ca ||*⁴

Grhapraveśa and *vāstuśāntipuja* are considered to be very important in a person's life, because he has to live happily and comfortably in the house. The auspicious effect of a house will continue to affect a person throughout his life as long as the person resides in that house. It is also mentioned in the *MatsyaPurāna* that the owner of the house must consider the auspicious time, *nakṣatra* etc. for entering the house, after which, *vāstu devatas* have to be appeased through the performance of *balikarma* and *samidha*:

*vāstauparīkṣitesamyagvāstudehavicakṣaṇāḥ ||
vāstūpaśamanaṅkuryātsamidbhirbalikarmaṅā ||*⁵

According to the scriptures, entering the house in the month of *Mārgaśīrṣa* and *Kārtika* is generally fruitful. The best results are seen in the months of *Phālguna*, *Vaiśākha* and *Jyeṣṭha*. At the time of *Grhapraveśa*, the rise of Jupiter and Venus is necessary and beneficial. The *nakṣatras*— *dhanīṣṭhā*, *puṣya*, *śatabhiṣā*, *svātī*, *aśvinī*, *anurādhā* and *hasta* are considered auspicious for performing the house warming *pūjā*. Apart from these, it is auspicious to enter the house on Monday, Wednesday, Thursday, Friday and Saturday. *Riktatithi*(*pournami*), *caturthī*, *navamī*, *caturdaśī*(4, 9, 14) and *amāvāsyātithī* should be avoided for *grhapraveśa*. On the remaining dates, *grhapraveśa* during day and night is considered to give good and auspicious results.

*praveśomadhyamojñeyaḥsaunyakārtikamāsayoḥ |
māghaphālgunavaiśākhaḥjyeṣṭhamāseṣuśobhanaḥ ||
śubhaḥpraveśodevejyaśukrayordṛśyamānayoḥ |*

vasvijavārūṇasvātīdāsrāmaitrakaroḍupu ||
vyarkāravāratithiṣuriktāmāvarjiteṣu ca |
*divāvāyadivārātraupraveśomaṅgalapradah ||*⁶

Benefits of Gṛhapraveśain different months:

Entering the house in the month of *Māgha* is said to give financial gain; in the month of *Phālguna*, happiness and will beget a son; in the month of *Caitra*, loss of money; in the month of *Vaiśākha* increase in wealth and grains; in the month of *Jyeṣṭha* there is benefit in livestock and happiness of children; entering the house in the months of *Āṣāḍha*, *Śrāvaṇa*, *Bhādrapada*, *Āśvina* and *Pauṣa* leads to loss of money and fear of enemies; in all the months from *saptamī* of *śuklapakṣa* to *aṣṭamī* of *kṛṣṇapakṣa*, entering the house gives beneficial and auspicious results:

māghe'rthalābhaḥprathamapraveṣeputrārthalābhaḥkhaluphālgune ca |
caitre'rthahānirdhanadhānyalābhovaiśākhāmāsepaśuputralābhaḥ ||
jyeṣṭhe ca māseṣupareṣunūnaṅhānipradahśatrubhayapradāśca |
*śukle ca pakṣeṣutarāṅvivṛddhyaikṛṣṇe ca yāvaddaśamīṅ ca tāvat ||*⁷

Procedure for Vāstumaṅḍala and pūjā for gṛhapraveśa and Vāstuśānti:

In any building, for *vāstuśānti*, a diagram of *sarvatobhadra*, *navagraha* etc. should be drawn with cow dung in the central part of that building and a *pūjākalaśa* (*Varuṇadeva*) with flowers and gold should be established at the place of worship:

maṅḍalaṅvāstunomadhyegomayenaprakalpayet |
*kalaśaṅmatravinyasyetsaprasūnaṅsakāñcanam ||*⁸

According to Ācārya Maya, twenty-five *kalaśas* containing water, gems and gold should be installed on the *vāstupūjanaupapīṭha* and all these *kalaśas* should be covered with new clothes:

kalaśāṅpañcakapañca, vāriyuktāṅnavavastrāṅmaṅihemasāṅyutān |
*matimāṅsālīgirausatāṅḍulehyupapīṭhetupadenyasettataḥ ||*⁹

According to the *Bṛhannāradyapurāṇa* (one of the eighteen Minor *purāṇas* (i.e., *Upapurāṇa*) according to the *Devībhāgavatapurāṇa* and other traditional lists of purāṇic literature), to create *Vāstupadamaṅḍala*, ten lines each should be drawn in the middle of the house using palmistry in the east-northeast and south-northeast. In this way, there will be approximately eighty-one posts on which rice should be kept. Forty-five deities should be seated in the *vāstumaṅḍala* thus created. Of these, thirty-two gods will be outside i.e. in the provincial chamber and thirteen gods will be inside.

*hastamātramlikhedrekhāṁdaśapūrvādaśottarāḥ |
grhamadhyetaṅduloparyekāśītipadaṁbhavet ||
pañcīttarānvakṣyamāṅāmścatvāriṁśatsurāṅnyaset |
dvātriṁśadvāhyatahpūjyāstatrāntaḥsthāstrayodaśā ||¹⁰*

According to Bhojadeva, to create *vāstumaṅḍala*, one should imagine the *vāstu* Gods directed in *catuḥṣaṣṭipada* on the *vāstupīṭha* at the same place. And then all the gods and goddesses of *vāstu* should be worshiped as per the rituals with incense, lamp, *naivedya* and various types of floral ornaments:

vāstudevastahkalpyayathasthanniyogath |

sadhuparvividhairmalyairarghyampaschannivedayet ||¹¹

According to the *MatsyaPurāṇa*, for *vāstuśānti* a *vāstumaṅḍalcakra* with *ekāśīti pada* should be made in the central part of the house. Then a *yajñakuṅḍa* of one hand deep and one hand wide, should be made, which should be equipped with three *mekhalās* (*mekhalās*) and *homa* should be performed in it with the help of *yava* (barley), black sesame seeds and milky trees (*vaṭa*, *pākaḍa*, *pīpala*, *gūlaraetc.*). *Samidha* of *palāśa* or *khādira* should be coated with honey and ghee. *kuśa*, *dūrvā* and *pañcabilva-phala* or their seeds should also be used in *vāstuśāntihavana*.

ekāśītipadaṁlikhyavāstumadhye ca prṣṭhataḥ ||

homastrimekhalekāryaḥkuṅḍehastapramāṅake |

yavaiḥkrṣṇatilaistadvatsamidbhiḥkṣīravṛkṣajaiḥ ||

pālāsaiḥkhādiraiścāpimadhusarpiḥsamanvitaiḥ |

kāyastupañcabhirbilvairbilvabījairathāpivā ||¹²

The method of sacrifice to all the gods located in the *vāstu pada* is described in detail in the *vāstu* texts. In *Matsyapurāṇa*¹³, *Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra*¹⁴ and *Mayamatam*¹⁵, there is a detailed description of the topics related to *vāstuśānti* for and *grhapraveśa* and worship of all the *vāstu* deities, offerings, sacrifices etc.

Balikarma (worship, worship and offering) of all the *Vāstu* gods situated in different *vāstupadas* should be done as per the rituals. Under all *Vāstupadas*, the sacrifice to the deities should be done in the common *āhatyamārga* (separate *Pūjā* and offering as per each deity). In *balikarma*, gods like *Brahmā* etc. should be worshiped in the proper sequence. Like in *vāstupadamaṇḍala*, first of all in *balikarma*, worship of *Brahmāsthāna* should be done duly with garland, incense, milk, honey, ghee, kheer and rice, etc. In this sequence, the gods located around *Brahmā* should be worshiped sequentially.

If it is not possible to perform the *pūjā* as per the above mentioned method, then in general, pure food and milk along with ghee should be offered to all the gods as a simple sacrifice. Fragrances, flowers etc. should also be provided to all the gods respectively.

All the *vāstudevatās* should be worshiped separately by taking their names in sequence. 'Om' should be used before the names of all the *vāstu* deities and 'namaḥ' should be added after the name and while meditating and worshipping, the worship material should be offered to those deities by taking their names. All objective deities should first be offered water and then ordinary sacrifices, after which special sacrifices should be offered to them and water should be offered again. According to ancient Acharyas, sacrifices and worship should also be offered to the deities located in villages, *maṇḍūka* (*catuḥṣaṣṭi*) *vāstupada* and *paramaśāyikavāstupada*.

According to *BrhannāradyaPurāṇa*, the image of *vāstupuruṣa* should be made with gold equal to the *pala* or half *pala* or quarter *pala*. The form of *vāstupuruṣa* should be made with two arms, three eyes and in a sleeping position. Then the image should be covered with a blood-cloth and worshiped with sesame seeds, rice mixed with incense and flowers.

palamānasuvarṇenatadarddhārdhanavāpunah |
pratimāvāstupuruṣasyadvibhujāṃ ca trinetrakām ||
śayanākārāmityevaṃraktavastreṇaveṣṭayet |
*tilataṇḍulasammiśraṇmaṇḍalegandhapuṣpakaiḥ ||*¹⁶

According to the scriptures, worship and worship of *vāstupuruṣa* and all the deities within the circle should be done as per the prescribed rituals, with full faith and devotion. Then one should pray to Lord *vāstupuruṣa* and all the gods thus 'O *VāstuPuruṣaBhagavān* who sleeps on the bed of land! I salute you. Lord! Please make my residence prosperous with money and grains etc.':

omvāstupūruṣa!namaste'stubhūśayānirata! prabho |
madagrhaṃdhanadhānyādisamṛddhaṃ kuru sarvadā ||
*itiprārthyatatodadyāddakṣiṇāmarcakāya ca ||*¹⁷

While praying thus, the best Brahmins should also be given *Dakṣiṇā*, jewelry etc. Apart from this, other *vāstu* worship should be done as per one's capacity.

According to one's financial capacity, all human beings should perform *Havana*, *balikarma* etc. for the nine planets, family deities etc. in *vāstupūjā*. In the *vāstuśānti*, performing *homa* (*yajña*) with materials like emulsion and jaggery etc. is beneficial. For *yajña*, liquids like *Apamārga* (cicada), *Palāśa* (kinshuk), *Khadira* (catechu wood), sesame, *akṣata* should be taken in *samidha*. A total of eight thousand or one hundred more offerings are made to all the deities together. Auspicious sounds like conch, bell etc. should be played in the house. In the new house, the new house should be cleaned by reciting *mantras* like *Śāntipāṭha*, *pañcadurgāpāṭha*, *śrīsūkta*, *śrīrudrasūkta*, *śrīpuruṣasūkta*, *pañcabrahmā* etc. The owner of the house should seek the blessings of the best Brahmins and ritualists who have got the *vāstupūjā* done by providing them adequate amount of money. After performing all the rituals like *pūjā*, *homa* etc., the owner of the house should first organize Brahmin feast and *Kanyā* feast with full devotion and then he should eat the meal with his relatives.

According to the *MatsyaPurāṇa*, after duly worshipping all the objective deities, for auspicious peace in the house, the best Brahmins should also be worshiped with devotion, and by giving them a water-filled pot decorated with curd, intact mangoes, flowers and fruits and to other Brahmins. The owner of the house should enter the house after offering gold, cow, gold jewelry, earth, food and clothes with reverence and devotion:

*kṛtvāgratodvijavarānathapūrṇakumbhaṃ
dadhyakṣatāmradalapuspaphalopaśobham ।
dattvāhiraṇyavasānānitadādvijebhyo
māṅgalyaśāntinilayāyagrhaṃviṣettu ॥¹⁸*

Even in the *Bṛhatsaṃhitā*, the method of *vāstuśānti*, *grhapraveśa* has been given in a brief and concise form. According to Acārya VarāhaMihira, it is auspicious for the owner of the house to enter the house which has been worshiped by flowers, *yajña* (*homa*) and consecrated by the worship of Gods and by the sound of recitation of Vedas by the Brahmins:

*bhūripuṣpavikiraṇasatorāṇaṃtoyapūrṇakalāśopaśobhitam ।
dhūpagandhabalipūjitāmaraṇbrāhmaṇadhvaniyutaṃviśedgrham ॥¹⁹*

Thus, when *vāstuśānti*, *grhapraveśa* and *grahaśānti* is done in a proper manner with full faith and devotion, the owner of the house gets the benefits of health, son, wealth and grains and lives happily in his house for the rest of his life. A person who enters a new house without performing *vāstupūjā* has to face many diseases, troubles and various kinds of troubles. One should not enter a house which has no doors, no roof and where no sacrifice has been made, because such a house is a storehouse of calamities:

*evanyahkurutesamyakgrhasāntimnrpottamaḥ |
 ārogyaṃputralābhaṃdhanamdhānyamlabhennaraḥ ||
 akṛtvavāstupūjānyahpraviśennavamandiram |
 rogāmnānāvidhānkleśānaśrutesarvasaṅkaṭam ||²⁰*

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this research paper has explored various aspects of *grhapraveśa* and *vāstuśānti* rituals to be performed by a resident at the time of construction or entry into the new construction. The rituals are designed so as to mitigate the disturbance created in the five elements of nature, honour the architects and the builders of the house or the construction. The various Gods residing in the place and the *Vāstudevatās* are appeased. The positive energy is enhanced in the house for a happy living. The priests, neighbours and relatives are also appeased with a feast.

End Notes:

1. *VāstuRatnākara*, 11. 67.
2. *ibid.*, 11. 67
3. *VālmīkiRāmāyaṇa*, 1. 27
4. *MatsyaPurāṇa*, 268. 3,4
5. *ibid.*, 268.2-3
6. *VāstuRatnākara*, 10.2-4
7. *ibid.*, 10.5,6
8. *SamarāṅgaṇaSūtradhāra*, 36.2
9. *Mayamatam*, 28.7
10. *VāstuSaukhyam*, 17. 1,2
11. *SamarāṅgaṇaSūtradhāra*, 36.3
12. *MatsyaPurāṇa*, 268.5-7
13. *ibid.*, 268.9-32
14. *SamarāṅgaṇaSūtradhāra*, 36.1-28
15. *Mayamatam*, 328.1-36
16. *VāstuSaukhyam*, 17.17,18
17. *ibid.*, 17. 19

18. *MatsyaPurāṇa*, 257. 22-3
19. *Br̥hatSam̥hitā, Vāstuvīdyāadhyāya*. 53.123
20. *VāstuSaukhyam*, 17.25-27

Bibliography:

1. *Br̥hatSam̥hitā* of Varāhamihira, M. RamakrishnaBhat, M.B.D. Electronic Printing Works, Bangalore, 1946.
2. *Br̥hatSam̥hitā*, Pandita AchyutanandaJha, ChaukhambaVidyabhawan, Varanasi, 2014.
3. *VāstuMaṇḍanam*, Dr. AnasuyaBhowmick, Indira Gandhi National Centre for Arts, New Delhi and Motilal Banarsidas PVT. LTD, Delhi, 2017.
4. *Mayamatam* Vol. 1, DagensBruno, Indira Gandhi National Centre for Arts, New Delhi and Motilal Banarsidas PVT. LTD, Delhi, 1994.
5. *Mayamatam*, Vol. 2, DagensBruno, Indira Gandhi National Centre for Arts, New Delhi and Motilal Banarsidas PVT. LTD, Delhi, 1994.
6. *VāstuRatnākara* (with Original Sanskrit Text, Translation, and Critical Notes), S. P. Deshpande, Jaico Publishing House, Mumbai, 2015.
7. *VāstuRatnākara*, Sri Bindhyeswari PrasadDwivedi,, Choukhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi, 1988.
8. *Br̥hannārādīyapurāṇam*, TarinisaJha, Hindi SahityaSammelana, Prayāga, 1989.
9. *MatsyaPurāṇa*, K. L. Joshi, (with an exhaustive introduction, Sanskrit text, English translation, and index of verses), Parimal Publication PVT. LTD., Delhi, 2023.
10. *VāstuSaukhyam*, Dr. Shri KrishnaJugnu, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi, 2017.
11. *SamarāṅgaṇaSūtradhāra* Vol. 1, Prof. PushpendraKumar, New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi, 1998.
12. *SamarāṅgaṇaSūtradhāra* Vol. 2, Prof. PushpendraKumar, New Bharatiya Book Corporation, Delhi, 1998.
13. *VāstuSaukhyam*, Dr. ShailajaPandeya,, Ganganath Jha Campus Publications, Prayagraj, 1993.

14. Pusalkar, A.D. *Studies in the Epics and Purāṇas of India*, Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan, Mumbai, 1967.
15. Rao, N. S., “*VāstuRatnākara: Principles of Ancient Indian Architecture*”, Oriental Book House, Hyderabad, 2008.
16. *SamarāṅgaṇaSūtradhāra*, Ganapati T.Sastri, Oriental Institute, Baroda, 1966.
17. *Rāmāyaṇam*, VāsudevaLakṣmaṇaŚāstri, (With TilakaṬīkā), NirṇayaSāgar Press, Mumbai, 1930.
18. Sharma, Sudarshan. “*Vāstuśāstra: Ancient Science of Architecture.*” Motilal Banarsidass Publishers, 2005.
19. *MatsyaPurāṇa*, Ed by Shastri, Sri RamapratapTripathy, Hindi SahityaSammelana, Prayāga, 2003.
20. *VāstuSukhyam*, Acarya Sri KamalakantaSukla, SikshanaShodhaPrakashanSansthan, Sampumananda Sanskrit University, Varanasi, 1996.

